

IMPROVING THE PROCESSES OF SHAPING OUTER CLOTHING DETAILS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8384440>

Abstract. *The article provides information about the processes of formation and improvement of garments based on resource-efficient technologies.*

Keywords: *Material, canvas, wet heat treatment, press, resource-saving, steam, knot, jacket, blazer, dublerin.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРОЦЕССОВ ПРИДАНИЯ ФОРМЫ ДЕТАЛЯМ ВЕРХНЕЙ ОДЕЖДЫ

Аннотация. *В статье представлена информация о процессах формирования и совершенствования швейных изделий на основе ресурсосберегающих технологий.*

Ключевые слова: *Материал, холст, влажно-термическая обработка, пресс, ресурсосберегающий, паровой, трикотаж, жакет, блейзер, Дублин.*

Nowadays, special attention is being paid to the production of textiles and sewing-knitting materials by using new technologies to improve their quality and produce ready-made products.

Garments are mainly made of flat materials, with a large proportion of them being fabrics and knitted fabrics. The use of non-woven materials in the garment industry is also growing rapidly.

However, recently there has been a lot of research into completely new processing technologies to solve the problems associated with garment design and manufacture. These works are based on the principles of turning the process of fabric and garment preparation into a continuous single technological process [1].

Such a technology allows to automate the process of making clothes without fabric preparation, cutting and sewing processes and to significantly reduce production waste. First of all, it belongs to the expanding sewing and knitting industry.

Based on the analysis of the methods of clothing preparation, along with the development of new technologies and equipment, the main directions of development of the sewing industry were clarified. The basis of the promising technology is the effective use of the shape-forming properties of the textile materials used in the preparation of the parts of the garment and the knots of the garment [2].

Changes in fashion and the recent emergence of new types of materials have created a need for new modes and premiums of wet heat treatment in the production of high-quality products. The implementation of wet-heat treatment of products in new regimes, in turn, required the development and appearance of new equipment and technological tools on the market.

Modern equipment for wet-heat treatment of sewing items includes various constructions according to functional purpose. These include carousel machines, ironing tables, mannequins, steam generators used between operations and in Intermittent Wet Heat Treatment (NIIB) for complex garments [3].

Different types of irons are used for dry ironing, steam ironing, irons with a special purpose for ironing certain knots, and various press equipment.

During wet-heat processing of men's outerwear, each part of the clothing details is treated with special press equipment. This is very important in the process of making clothes.

It is important to reduce the number of operations in the process of making clothes and use efficient technologies. For this reason, on the basis of the analysis of the methods of preparing clothes, along with the development of new technologies and equipment, the main directions of development of the sewing industry were determined. The basis of the promising technology is the effective use of the shape-forming properties of the textile materials used in the preparation of the parts of the garment and the knots of the garment.

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